

Urban vacancy: mapping the European research landscape

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Abstract

Although still a niche within established disciplines, research on urban vacancy has boomed in recent decades, with different research communities investigating different dimensions of vacancy. However, these communities rarely communicate with each other, leading to parallel debates, different conceptual vocabularies and diverging empirical foci. This becomes particularly problematic in the current era, which is best characterised not simply as an ‘urban age’, but as one in which city regions find themselves at the heart of economic, ecological and societal crises that are reshaping our world. Vacant spaces can be understood as symptoms of these crises, but also as actually existing and potential sites for experimentation, prefiguring new and more sustainable ways of urban living. The current paper offers a mapping and review of research publications and projects across Europe, identifying similarities and differences between regions with regard to research output, empirical foci and theoretical concerns. Cutting across different research domains, the paper concludes by proposing an integrated and interdisciplinary European research agenda on urban vacancy.

Keywords

Vacancy, urban and regional development, public policy and planning, research

Introduction

In an excellent paper on vacancy within the urbanisation process, Cian O’Callaghan (2023) rightly highlights that research on vacant land and property has occupied a somewhat ambivalent position within urban scholarship: on the one hand, with urban studies and planning having paid attention throughout their history to urban decline and uneven urban development; on the other hand, with urban vacancy rarely being the core focus. Research on urban vacancy is also relatively fragmented, with different research communities linked to specific dimensions of the urban vacancy problem, be it empty housing, urban ruins, temporary use, brownfield development, urban sprawl or ecosystems services (and many more topics). However, these communities rarely communicate with each other, leading to parallel debates, different conceptual vocabularies and diverging empirical foci. As city regions contribute to many of the complex and intertwined economic, ecological and societal crises we currently face, yet also offer more or less radical solutions to these crises, this is a debilitating state of research. To develop a stronger, more integrated research perspective—both conceptually and empirically—this paper offers a review of existing literature, with a specific

focus on the European context. I am particularly interested in identifying similarities and differences between regions with regard to research output, empirical foci and theoretical concerns, as most research to date has been oriented towards individual case studies, with only a limited tradition of international comparative analysis (exceptions of course exist, e.g., Álvarez de Andrés et al., 2019; Anguelovski, 2013; Marraccini et al., 2015; Martínez López, 2013; Adams et al., 2010).

In order to map the research output of different research communities across the social sciences and humanities, I conducted a synthetic review of the available literature on urban vacancy. Considering the attention paid to urban vacancy in academic research, policy circles and civic networks over the last four decades, it is somewhat surprising that almost no substantial literature reviews exist on the topic, with the vast majority of research output focusing on individual case studies or specific dimensions of vacancy (e.g., shrinking cities, squatting or temporary use). To the best of my knowledge, this paper therefore offers the first ever large-scale review of urban vacancy research. Methodologically, my approach consisted of three steps. First, I compiled a dataset based on the Scopus database to identify publications dealing with urban vacancy in cities and regions across Europe. This already offers relevant insights into the *geography* of research on the topic, the main journals in which works on vacancy are published and the key issues addressed in relation to urban vacancy. Importantly, tracing publication output over multiple decades (from 1977 onwards) allows the identification of both the shifting geography of knowledge production and the research foci. Second, I extracted data from two key European databases—the European Commission’s repository for EU Framework Programme projects (CORDIS) and the Keep.eu database for information on Interreg projects—to analyse the contribution of more applied and often policy-oriented research projects to the knowledge about urban vacancy in Europe. Work conducted within these projects often does not translate into publications in Scopus-registered outlets, even though many projects are referenced in the wider policy and civic debates. Third, and building on the largely quantitative review of the three databases, I conducted a qualitative, thematic analysis of transversal themes that are shared across multiple research fields, projects and publications. The following sections discuss each step in turn. In the final section, I conclude by offering preliminary notes on a future research agenda for urban vacancy in Europe.

European publications: Scopus

To compile a dataset of publications on urban vacancy, I relied on the Scopus database. Scopus tends to provide a wider coverage than Web of Science for the social sciences and humanities, and scores better with regard to the inclusion of publications in languages other than English. Google Scholar has even wider coverage, but lacks the quality control needed for bibliometric analysis. An initial search (within ‘article title, abstracts, keywords’) was conducted on 27

November 2024, using two combined search strings: 'urban OR city OR cities' AND 'vacancy OR vacant OR empty OR abandoned OR abandonment OR brownfield OR derelict OR blight OR infill OR ruins OR shrinking OR interstitial OR wasteland'. My familiarity with the literature shows these terms to be predominantly used when discussing the topic, and this applies to all the research communities involved. Executing this search string within the Scopus subject area 'Social Sciences' produced a total of 10,208 documents, with more than 2,600 linked to the US; a reflection both of the dominance of North America within the global system of academic knowledge production and of its early interest in urban vacancy compared with other countries. As my core research concern focuses on the European setting, I further narrowed down the search by only selecting European countries,¹ leading to a dataset of 4,377 documents.

In line with the overall trend of a substantial increase in publication quantity over the last two decades, most items on urban vacancy in Europe were published in the last 20 years, and particularly in the last 10. The first registered publication in Scopus is a 1977 *Geoforum* paper in French, titled 'L'organisation capitaliste du territoire et le problème du logement en Italie' (Dematteis et al., 1977), addressing the contradiction between the presence of unused or underused building stock and the existence of many sub-standard and overcrowded houses. For the subsequent decades, publications on urban vacancy tend to remain within the realm of single digits, and it is only from the early 2000s onwards that output starts increasing rapidly, up to an average of more than 350 publications per year in the 2020s. Although globally the US is the main producer of publications on urban vacancy, in Europe most of these are linked via the authors to the United Kingdom, Italy or Germany (see Figure 1). These three countries together account for 49 per cent of all European publications in the dataset. As Figure 1 shows, the North-South and West-East divides often observed in the European publication landscape do not really hold in the case of research on urban vacancy, since we can observe a reasonable geographical distribution across European space.

¹ At this stage, I had to use the proxy of 'country affiliation of the author(s)', as Scopus does not identify the country/region/city that is at the core of the analysis in each paper. This is the only way to focus geographically, but I recognise the limitations of potentially: a) including papers not dealing with Europe yet written by authors based in European countries, and b) excluding papers dealing with urban vacancy in Europe yet written by authors based outside Europe.

Figure 1: Countries with the highest number of Scopus-registered documents on urban vacancy

Analysing basic bibliometric data is an important and already insightful first step, but a more detailed analysis necessitates drilling down further. As comprehensively reviewing 4,377 documents is all but impossible, I adopted a further reduction strategy of removing from the dataset all publications with fewer than 50 citations. The underlying rationale for this decision is that papers with fewer citations may be interesting and important, but they are unlikely to shape the wider academic debate on urban vacancy (which most have also failed to do in the past 20–30 years). An exception was made for papers from the most recent five-year period, as it often takes several years to gain a reasonable number of citations. For these papers, I chose a cut-off point of at least 15 citations (time period 2019–2023, as no papers from 2024 had yet received 15 or more citations). The documents were then manually checked for eligibility by reading the titles, keywords and abstracts of each. Papers were removed from the list if they did not focus on a European setting, did not sufficiently address social scientific concerns (e.g., technical papers on building design or remote sensing) and/or there was no actual focus on vacant urban spaces. An example would be a paper that dealt with cities and contained the term ‘abandoned’, but used it to claim that theories should be abandoned. Removing ineligible papers led to a list of 163 documents for the overall time period and 114 documents for the 2019–2023 period.

Table 1 shows the top most-cited publications from the overall time period list.² Various publications focus on shrinking cities, including that by Martinez-Fernandez et al. (2012),

² Due to length restrictions, only a selection of publications is shown in the tables and figures or referenced in this paper. The full dataset is available on request.

which is the most-cited paper in the complete dataset. Work on urban ruins and aesthetics also returns, as does research on land use change and ecology—especially (but not only) in Mediterranean contexts—temporary use, squatting and brownfield redevelopment.

Rank	Authors	Title	Year	Source title	Country affiliation(s)
1	Martinez-Fernandez et al.	Shrinking Cities: Urban Challenges of Globalization	2012	IJURR	FR, AU, US
2	Kaika, Swyngedouw	Fetishizing the modern city: The phantasmagoria of ...	2000	IJURR	UK
3	Wiechmann, Pallagst	Urban shrinkage in Germany and the USA: ...	2012	IJURR	DE
4	Meyfroidt et al.	Middle-range theories of land system change	2018	Global Environmental Change	BE, US, CH, AT, NL, AU, DE, CA, SE
5	Edensor	The ghosts of industrial ruins: Ordering and ...	2005	Environment and Planning D	UK
6	Haase et al.	Conceptualizing urban shrinkage	2014	Environment and Planning A	DE, UK
7	Fields, Uffer	The financialisation of rental housing: A comparative ...	2016	Urban Studies	UK, US
8	Serra et al.	Beyond urban-rural dichotomy: Exploring ...	2014	Applied Geography	ES, IT
9	Haase et al.	Varieties of shrinkage in European cities	2016	European Urban and Regional Studies	DE, UK
10	Tonkss	Austerity urbanism and the makeshift city	2013	City	UK
11	Bontje	Facing the challenge of shrinking cities in East ...	2004	GeoJournal	NL
12	Pratt	Urban regeneration: From the arts 'feel good' factor ...	2009	Urban Studies	UK
13	Wolff, Wiechmann	Urban growth and decline: Europe's shrinking cities ...	2018	European Urban and Regional Studies	DE
14	Martinez-Fernandez et al.	Shrinking cities in Australia, Japan, Europe and the ...	2016	Progress in Planning	FR, AU, US, DE, JP
15	Großmann et al.	Shrinking cities: Notes for the further research agenda	2013	Cities	DE, UK, NL
16	Macintyre et al.	Do poorer people have poorer access to local ...	2008	Social Science and Medicine	UK
17	Bernt	Partnerships for demolition: The governance of urban ...	2009	IJURR	DE
18	Groth, Corijn	Reclaiming urbanity: Indeterminate spaces, informal ...	2005	Urban Studies	BE
19	Quintas-Soriano et al.	Impacts of land use change on ecosystem services ...	2016	Land Use Policy	ES, US
20	Dehaene, De Cauter	Heterotopia and the city: Public space in a postcivil ...	2008		NL, BE
21	Orueta, Feinstein	The new mega-projects: Genesis and impacts	2008	IJURR	ES, US
22	Mah	Industrial ruination, community, and place: ...	2012		UK
23	Rieniets	Shrinking cities: Causes and effects of urban ...	2009	Nature and Culture	CH
24	González-García et al.	Quantifying spatial supply-demand mismatches in ...	2020	Land Use Policy	ES
25	Sailer-Fliege	Characteristics of post-socialist urban transformation ...	1999	GeoJournal	DE
26	Haase et al.	Conceptualizing the nexus between urban shrinkage ...	2014	Landscape and Urban Planning	DE
27	Wiechmann	Errors Expected - Aligning Urban Strategy with ...	2008	International Planning Studies	DE
28	Hospers	Policy Responses to Urban Shrinkage: From Growth ...	2014	European Planning Studies	NL
29	Edensor	Mundane hauntings: Commuting through the ...	2008	Cultural Geographies	UK
30	Gandy	Marginalia: Aesthetics, Ecology, and Urban Wastelands	2013	Annals of the AAG	UK
31	Schetke, Haase	Multi-criteria assessment of socio-environmental ...	2008	Environmental Impact Assessment Review	DE
32	Couch, Dennemann	Urban regeneration and sustainable development in ...	2000	Cities	UK
33	Mudu	Resisting and challenging neoliberalism: The ...	2004	Antipode	IT
34	Pruijt	Is the institutionalization of urban movements ...	2003	IJURR	NL
35	Jorgensen, Tylecote	Ambivalent landscapes - Wilderness in the urban ...	2007	Landscape Research	UK
36	Fischer et al.	Beyond green: Broad support for biodiversity in ...	2018	Global Environmental Change	DE, SI, SE, IT, US, DK, NL
37	Salvati et al.	To grow or to sprawl? Land Cover Relationships in a ...	2013	Cities	IT
38	Evans	'Rabbit Hutches on Postage Stamps': Planning, ...	1991	Urban Studies	UK
39	Kroll, Kabisch	The Relation of Diverging Urban Growth Processes ...	2012	Population, Space and Place	DE
40	García-Lamarca	From Occupying Plazas to Recuperating Housing: ...	2017	IJURR	ES
41	Ball	Re-use potential and vacant industrial premises: ...	2002	Journal of Property Research	UK
42	Hubbard	The battle for the high street: Retail gentrification, ...	2017		UK
43	Mallach et al.	The shrinking city in comparative perspective: ...	2017	Cities	DE, US, JP
44	Parcerisas et al.	Land use changes, landscape ecology and their ...	2012	Environmental Science and Policy	ES
45	Solana-Solana	Rural gentrification in Catalonia, Spain: A case study ...	2010	Geoforum	ES
46	Sousa, Pinho	Planning for Shrinkage: Paradox or Paradigm	2015	European Planning Studies	PT
47	La Rosa et al.	Agriculture and the city: A method for sustainable ...	2014	Land Use Policy	IT
48	Moss	Cold spots' of urban infrastructure: 'Shrinking' ...	2008	IJURR	DE
49	Adams et al.	Brownfield development: A comparison of North ...	2010	Urban Studies	UK, US
50	Rousseau	Re-imagining the city centre for the middle classes: ...	2009	IJURR	FR

Table 1: Top most-cited publications based on Scopus (overall time period)

The *International Journal of Urban and Regional Research* (IJURR) is the leading journal for the most-cited publications on urban vacancy, followed by *Cities*, *Urban Studies*, *European Planning Studies* and *Land Use Policy*. In line with the earlier analysis, articles by authors based in the UK, Italy or Germany also belong to the most-cited publications in the dataset. By contrast, among the most-cited publications there are very few authors affiliated with Central or Eastern European institutions. Highly cited output is thus not only linked to journals with a strong international profile (and therefore potentially a 'global' readership), but seemingly also to country affiliation, with authors based in Western or Southern European countries having most citations.

Table 2 zooms in on the more recent (2019–2023) publications. With regard to research topics, a continued interest in the original topics is visible in the overall list. New topics also seem to be emerging, although it is difficult to predict to what extent these already are or will become substantial research strands within the body of work on urban vacancy. This applies to new accents in housing research, such as work on short-term rental platforms, the regulatory and legal environment of public housing, the COVID-19 pandemic and its effects on urban space, and quite visibly research into the commons, often with specific interest paid to the role of migrants.

Rank	Authors	Title	Year	Source title	Country affiliation(s)
1	González-García et al.	Quantifying spatial supply-demand mismatches in ...	2020	Land Use Policy	ES
2	Döringer et al.	A meta-analysis of shrinking cities in Europe and Japan. ...	2020	European Planning Studies	AT, JP
3	Adamiak et al.	Airbnb offer in Spain-Spatial analysis of the pattern and ...	2019	ISPRS	PL, SE, ES
4	Quintas-Soriano et al.	Effects of land abandonment on nature contributions ...	2022	Land Use Policy	ES, DE
5	Pinto et al.	Ecosystem services and well-being dimensions related ...	2022	Sustainable Cities and Society	PT, LT, GR, SE
6	Grubbauer, Čamprag	Urban megaprojects, nation-state politics and regulatory ...	2019	Urban Studies	DE
7	Balletto et al.	A methodological approach on disused public properties ...	2021	Sustainability (Switzerland)	IT
8	Palliwoda et al.	How do the green components of urban green ...	2020	Landscape Ecology	DE
9	Phillips et al.	Re-placing displacement in gentrification studies: ...	2021	Geoforum	UK
10	Atkinson	Necrotecture: Lifeless Dwellings and London's Super-Rich ...	2019	IJURR	UK
11	De Valck et al.	Valuing urban ecosystem services in sustainable ...	2019	Ecosystem Services	NL, BE, AU
12	Washbourne et al.	Trade-offs and synergies in the ecosystem service ...	2020	Ecosystem Services	UK, DE
13	Guastella et al.	Patterns of urban spatial expansion in European Cities ...	2019	Sustainability (Switzerland)	IT, FR
14	Capolongo et al.	How to assess urban regeneration proposals by ...	2019	Sustainability (Switzerland)	IT
15	Haase et al.	Factors driving the regrowth of European cities and the ...	2021	Cities	DE, NL, PL, UK, CZ
16	Sikorski et al.	The value of doing nothing – How informal green spaces ...	2021	Ecosystem Services	PL
17	Szafrańska et al.	Urban shrinkage and housing in a post-socialist city: ...	2019	Journal of Housing and the Built Environment	PL, FR
18	Llorent-Bedmar et al.	The rural exodus of young people from empty Spain. ...	2021	Journal of Rural Studies	ES
19	Jiménez-Olivencia et al.	Land use change dynamics in Euro-mediterranean ...	2021	Land Use Policy	ES, US
20	Montagna, Grazioli	Urban commons and freedom of movement. The housing ...	2019	Citizenship Studies	UK
21	Camerin	From "Ribera Plan" to "Diagonal Mar", passing through ...	2019	Land Use Policy	ES
22	Calvet-Mir, March	Crisis and post-crisis urban gardening initiatives from ...	2019	European Urban and Regional Studies	ES
23	Slach et al.	Urban shrinkage and sustainability: Assessing the nexus ...	2019	Sustainability (Switzerland)	CZ
24	Bosone et al.	Indicators for ex-post evaluation of cultural heritage ...	2021	Sustainability (Switzerland)	IT
25	Caparros-Midwood et al.	Low Carbon, Low Risk, Low Density: Resolving choices ...	2019	Cities	UK
26	Cerreta et al.	A creative living lab for the adaptive reuse of the morticelli ...	2020	Sustainability (Switzerland)	IT
27	Ferretti, Grosso	Designing successful urban regeneration strategies ...	2019	Cities	IT, UK
28	Arvanitidis, Papagiannitsis	Urban open spaces as a commons: The credibility thesis ...	2020	Cities	GR
29	Sylla et al.	Valuing environmental amenities in peri-urban areas: ...	2019	Sustainability (Switzerland)	PL, DE
30	Ortiz-Báez et al.	Characterizing landscape patterns in urban-rural ...	2021	Journal of Urban Management	BE, EC
31	Glumac, Islam	Housing preferences for adaptive re-use of office and ...	2020	Sustainable Cities and Society	LU
32	Bruns-Berentelg et al.	Developing urban growth and urban quality: ...	2022	Urban Studies	DE, DK, CN
33	Pallagst et al.	Shrinking cities: Implications for planning cultures? ...	2021	Urban Studies	DE, JP
34	Barreira et al.	Satisfied but thinking about leaving: the reasons behind ...	2019	International Journal of Urban Sciences	PT
35	Daly et al.	The impacts of tourism on cultural identity on Lisbon ...	2021	Journal of Ethnic and Cultural Studies	PT
36	Béal et al.	Varieties of right-sizing strategies: comparing degrowth ...	2019	Urban Geography	FR
37	Raimondi	For 'common struggles of migrants and locals'. Migrant ...	2019	Citizenship Studies	IT
38	Rovelli et al.	From railways to greenways: a complex index for ...	2020	Land Use Policy	IT
39	Somoza-Medina, Monteserín-Abella	The sustainability of industrial heritage tourism far from ...	2021	Sustainability (Switzerland)	ES
40	Coppola	Projects of becoming in a right-sizing shrinking City ...	2019	Urban Geography	IT
41	Eraydin, Özatağan	Pathways to a resilient future: A review of policy agendas ...	2021	Cities	TR
42	Esposito, Chiodelli	Juggling the formal and the informal: The regulatory ...	2020	Geoforum	IT
43	Bragaglia, Rossignolo	Temporary urbanism as a new policy strategy: a ...	2021	International Planning Studies	IT
44	Hubbard	Enthusiasm, craft and authenticity on the High Street: ...	2019	Social and Cultural Geography	UK
45	Rickardsson	The urban-rural divide in radical right populist support: ...	2021	Annals of Regional Science	SE
46	Sessa et al.	Opinion paper on green deal for the urban regeneration ...	2022	Land Use Policy	IT, UK
47	Manganelli et al.	The social cost of urban sprinkling ...	2020	Sustainability (Switzerland)	IT
48	Ferrari et al.	Conservation and enhancement of the green ...	2019	Urban Ecosystems	IT
49	Bisschops, Beunen	A new role for citizens' initiatives: the difficulties in ...	2019	Journal of Environmental Planning and Management	NL
50	Vannier et al.	Co-constructing future land-use scenarios for the ...	2019	Landscape and Urban Planning	FR

Table 2: Top most-cited publications based on Scopus (2019–2023 time period)

Whereas *Cities*, *Land Use Policy* and *European Planning Studies* remain popular publishing outlets for research on urban vacancy, *Urban Studies* only shows up a handful of times and *IJURR* has almost disappeared from the list of most-cited publications. Strikingly, its leading position has been taken over by the MDPI journal *Sustainability*. Whereas the most-cited publications are rarely from *Sustainability* in the overall list of 163 documents (the first

Sustainability publication is ranked number 108), in the 2019-2023 list of 114 documents it is by far the most-referenced journal (one in five papers).

Comparing Tables 1 and 2 is insightful, not just to observe thematic shifts, but also to analyse geographic shifts in research production. Figure 1 already shows that the United Kingdom, Italy and Germany together produce 49 per cent of all European publications in the dataset, but this hides the more recent decline of the UK and Germany and the strong increase in particular of output linked to Italian institutions: whereas only 8 per cent of publications in the overall list had at least one Italy-based author, this increased to 25 per cent in the 2019–2023 list. To varying degrees, this also applies to Spain (from 7 to 13 per cent), Poland (1 to 11 per cent) and Portugal (4 to 7 per cent). By contrast, the UK saw a decrease from 36 to 13 per cent and Germany from 28 to 14 per cent.³ It is beyond the remit of this paper to offer a complete explanation for this change, but it seems to be at least partially an effect of shifting thematic interests: especially for Germany, a large amount of research was published on shrinking cities in the early 2000s to mid-2010s, and many of these publications belong to the top-cited papers in our dataset. In the 2019–2023 period, this literature almost disappeared from the top-cited list and has only been partially replaced by other topics, leading to lower visibility for Germany-based researchers. The strong decline of the UK is more difficult to explain: having always been more diverse than the German debate, the 2019–2023 phase shows a clear reduction of publications on urban vacancy, but without an obvious cause. The same applies to Italy: no single theme dominated the 2019–2023 period, but we do see a strong growth of publication output that is also highly cited. This suggests a second argument, namely that the increase in cited publication output for Italy co-developed with (and may be partially explained by) a substantial increase in the number of papers published per year by journals such as *Sustainability*: in the 2019–2023 dataset, 35 per cent of all papers with at least one Italy-based author were published in *Sustainability* (the dataset average is 20 per cent).⁴ Lastly, compared with the total output as presented in Figure 1, showing a reasonable geographical distribution across European space, the datasets underlying Tables 1 and 2 show a much more skewed geography, with researchers based in Russia, Turkey and most parts of Southeast and Central Europe having, if any, few citations—mostly below the cut-off points of 50 or 15. In other words, whilst we can observe a diversification of the centres of research production, many countries clearly remain on the periphery with regard to publishing highly cited output. However, when we analyse the field of applied research on urban vacancy, to which I now turn, the situation may appear more equal.

³ Caution is needed, as these percentages are not directly comparable: they depend on the ultimately arbitrary cut-off points of at least 50 citations for the first list and 15 citations for the second one. Different cut-off points would lead to different percentages, though it seems unlikely that the trends observed here would be radically different.

⁴ The same observation can be made for Poland, but not Portugal or Spain.

European projects: CORDIS and Keep.eu

Research on urban vacancy involves both basic, academic research and applied, often policy-oriented work, the latter of which often does not lead to journal articles, book chapters or other publications registered in Scopus, but that are referenced in the wider debate and considered as good or not-so-good practices. Most review papers are limited to a quantitative or qualitative analysis of publication output as registered in scientific databases, but in the case of urban vacancy research this would be an inadmissible limitation and blind spot. To include this ‘grey literature’, I relied on two European databases: CORDIS and Keep.eu. Whereas the first is the European Commission’s public repository for projects funded by the EU’s framework programmes for research and innovation (FP, Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe), Keep.eu registers data on projects involving cross-border, transnational and interregional cooperation (Interreg and URBACT).

Both databases were searched using the same search string as the one used for Scopus. Following manual cleaning, 20 projects were retained (Table 3). Similar to the case of Scopus, only projects that had a substantive and social scientific focus on urban vacancy in Europe were retained. Overlap can be observed between the geography of research output as registered in Scopus and that of CORDIS-registered projects by looking at the country location of the partners involved. Of the 20 listed projects, the top three countries in Scopus (UK, Italy and Germany) also feature in many projects as partners (eight, nine and nine projects, respectively). In addition, many sub-top countries reoccur in this list as privileged project partners: the Netherlands (with ten projects, the most visible partner in this list), Poland (seven), France (seven) and Spain (six).

Acronym	Title	Period	Programme
GREENSCOM	Communicating urban growth and green	2000-2003	FP5
URBAN CATALYSTS	Strategies for temporary uses	2001-2003	FP5
RESCUE	Regeneration of European sites in cities and urban environments	2002-2005	FP5
CABERNET	Concerted action on brownfield and economic regeneration network	2002-2005	FP5
SHRINK SMART	Governance of shrinkage within a European context	2009-2012	FP7
PLANSHRINKING	Planning cultures in the USA and in Germany in comparison	2010-2014	FP7
URBLIV	Building just and livable cities	2011-2013	FP7
TIMBRE	Tailored Improvement for Brownfield Regeneration in Europe	2011-2014	FP7
EMUVE	Euro-Mediterranean Urban Voids Ecology	2013-2015	FP7
REPAiR	REsource Management in Peri-urban Areas	2016-2020	H2020
Local State	State Formation Through the Local Production of Property and Citizenship	2016-2021	H2020
RE-CITY	Reviving shrinking cities	2018-2022	H2020
PaDC	Property and Democratic Citizenship	2018-2024	H2020
gE.CO Living Lab	Generative European Commons Living Lab	2019-2022	H2020
PICTURING	Post-Industrial Chimneys seen Through Urban Regeneration Imaginaries	2020-2023	H2020
T-Factor	Unleashing future-facing urban hubs through culture and creativity-led strategies of transformative time	2020-2024	H2020
CENTRINNO	New CENTRalities in INdustrial areas as engines for inNOvation and urban transformation	2020-2024	H2020
HUB-IN	Hubs of Innovation and Entrepreneurship for the Transformation of Historic Urban Areas	2020-2025	H2020
NOMAD	Nomad MAnagement of Urban Development	2023-2025	HORIZON
DEPOP	Coping with decline	2024-2029	HORIZON

Table 3: Projects dealing with urban vacancy as registered in CORDIS

The thematic foci remained relatively stable throughout the years, with temporary use being tackled by one of the earliest and best-known European projects in the dataset (URBAN

CATALYSTS), to more recent research (NOMAD). Multiple projects also address the problems of shrinking cities (e.g., PLANSHRINKING, RE-CITY and DEPOP) or deal with industrial decline and brownfield regeneration, often in relation to greening concerns (e.g., GREENSCOM and TIMBRE). More recent debates on the circular economy (REPAiR) or the commons (gE.CO Living Lab) also become visible in relation to urban vacancy.

Mapping CORDIS-registered publication output on urban vacancy involved three steps. I first extracted from CORDIS the output linked to the 20 projects. Second, I used the same search string to scan the full CORDIS database in order to capture publications on urban vacancy but not linked to the 20 projects. Third, I looked up citation rates for each publication to understand the actual impact of these publications on the wider research landscape.⁵ Following the same manual cleaning criteria as for the previous steps led to a list of 60 publications in total, the most cited of which are presented in Table 4.

⁵ I used Google Scholar for this part of the exercise, as it has the widest coverage concerning publication types (precisely because it lacks 'quality control') and thus the highest likelihood of also including references to the 'grey literature' on urban vacancy. As a result, Table 4 and Tables 1 and 2 are not directly comparable, but the main goal of the table is to show the overlap between Scopus-registered and CORDIS-registered publications, as well as the extent to which important publications on urban vacancy are not captured by established scientific databases.

Rank	Authors	Title	Year	Source title	Country affiliation(s)
1	Wiechmann, Pallagst	Urban shrinkage in Germany and the USA: A Comparison ...	2012	International Journal of Urban and Regional Research	DE
2	Haase et al.	Actors and factors in land use simulation: the challenge ...	2012	Environmental Modelling & Software	DE
3	Angelovski	New directions in urban environmental justice: ...	2013	Journal of Planning Education and Research	ES
4	Birch, Mykhnenko	Varieties of neoliberalism? Restructuring in large ...	2009	Journal of Economic Geography	CA, UK
5	Pallagst	The planning research agenda: shrinking cities – a ...	2010	Town Planning Review	DE
6	Angelovski	From Environmental Trauma to Safe Haven: Place ...	2013	City and Community	ES
7	Frantál et al.	Location Matters! Exploring Brownfields Regeneration ...	2013	Moravian Geographical Reports	CZ
8	Kunc et al.	Destiny of Urban Brownfields: Spatial Patterns and ...	2014	Transylvanian Review of Administrative Sciences	CZ
9	Martinat et al.	Re-reuse of regenerated brownfields: Lessons from ...	2018	Journal of Cleaner Production	UK, CZ, US
10	Amenta, van Timmeren	Beyond Wastescapes: Towards Circular Landscapes. ...	2018	Sustainability	IT, NL
11	Cortinovis, Geneletti	Mapping and assessing ecosystem services to support ...	2018	One Ecosystem	IT
12	Alexandrescu et al.	The Path From Passivity Toward Entrepreneurship: ...	2014	Organization and Environment	RO, UK, CZ, DE
13	Morio et al.	Applying a multi-criteria genetic algorithm framework ...	2013	Journal of Environmental Management	DE
14	Oberstege et al.	Urban Regions Shifting to Circular Economy: ...	2019	Urban Planning	DE, BE, IT, PL, NL, HU
15	Amenta et al.	Managing the Transition towards Circular Metabolism: ...	2019	Urban Planning	NL, IT
16	Remøy et al.	Facilitating Circular Economy in Urban Planning	2019	Urban Planning	NL, PL
17	Angelovski	Beyond a livable and green neighborhood: Asserting ...	2013	International Journal of Urban and Regional Research	ES
18	Heurkens, Dąbrowski	Circling the square: Governance of the circular ...	2020	European Spatial Research and Policy	NL
19	Wandl et al.	The Circular Economy Concept in Design Education: ...	2019	Urban Planning	NL
20	Schädler et al.	Spatially explicit computation of sustainability indicator ...	2013	Landscape and Urban Planning	DE
21	Dąbrowski et al.	Transferring Circular Economy Solutions across ...	2019	Urban Planning	NL, HU, IT
22	Klusáček et al.	Regeneration of agricultural brownfields in the Czech ...	2013	Acta Universitatis Agriculturae et Silviculturae Mendelianae Brunensis	CZ
23	Arciniegas et al.	A Geodesign Decision Support Environment for ...	2019	Urban Planning	NL, DE
24	Ferri, Vasudevan	Vacancy at the edges of the precarious city	2019	Geoforum	IT, UK
25	van der Leer et al.	Social-Ecological-Technical systems in urban planning ...	2018	Architectural Science Review	SE, NL
26	Cerreta et al.	Regenerativescapes: Incremental Evaluation for the ...	2020	Sustainability	IT
27	Alexandrescu et al.	Transdisciplinarity in Practice: The Emergence and ...	2014	Interdisciplinary Science Reviews	IT, DE
28	Amenta, Qu	Experimenting with Circularity When Designing ...	2020	Sustainability	IT, NL
29	Rigillo et al.	Eco-Innovative Solutions for Wasted Landscapes. ...	2018	RI-VISTA	IT
30	Schemschat	Refugee Arrival under Conditions of Urban Decline: ...	2021	Sustainability	NL
31	Calza Bini et al.	Interconnessioni tra sviluppo economico e demografico ...	2010	Argomenti, The Journal of Economy, Culture and Social Research	IT
32	Varjú et al.	Local resource-based development potential as ...	2020	European Spatial Research and Policy	HU
33	Wolff et al.	The Role of Brownfields and Their Revitalisation for ...	2023	land	DE
34	Ivanov	Narratives of Crisis: How Framing Urban Shrinkage ...	2021	Sustainability	DE
35	Lewis et al.	Multifunctional Green Infrastructure in Shrinking ...	2022	Urban Planning	PT
36	Amenta	beyond WASTESCAPES: Opportunities for sustainable ...	2019		IT
37	Calza Bini	Quale sviluppo? Quale Locale? Ripensando i sistemi ...	2010	Argomenti, The Journal of Economy, Culture and Social Research	IT
38	Song et al.	Evaluating sustainable urban development using urban ...	2018	Europa XXI	NL
39	Garzilli et al.	Integrated Approaches for Peri-Urban Wastescapes	2020	International Journal of Urban Planning and Smart Cities	IT
40	Besana	Proposals of European Citizens for Reviving the Future ...	2019	Quaestiones Geographicae	LU, PL
41	Sakali, Karyotis	Can't #StayAtHome without a Home: Politics of housing ...	2022	Luchas invisibles en tiempos de pandemia II	BE
42	Cerreta et al.	A hybrid decision-making process for wastescapes ...	2018	Environmental and territorial modelling for planning and design	IT, NL
43	Matoga	Changing Governance Processes to Make Way for Civic ...	2022	Sustainability	DE
44	Bartke et al.	Das TIMBRE Priorisierungstool: Brachflächenbewertung ...	2014	altlasten spektrum	DE
45	Amenta, Lucertini	Urban Metabolism and Circular Economy interrelations. ...	2019	BDC - Bollettino Del Centro Calza Bini	IT, NL
46	Iodice, De Toro	Waste and Wasted Landscapes: Focus on Abandoned ...	2020	Detritus	BE, IT
47	Liu	Strategies for sustainability in shrinking cities: Frames ...	2021	Nordia Geographical Publications	DE
48	Berruti, Palestino	La pianificazione del ciclo dei rifiuti e delle aree rifiuto ...	2017	Rivista online di Urban@it	IT
49	Liu	Long-Term Development Perspectives in the Slow ...	2022	Sustainability	DE
50	Matyushkina	"Force Majeure": The Transformation of Cultural ...	2021	Urbana	DE

Table 4: Most-cited CORDIS-registered publications

In contrast to the Scopus-derived list of the most cited publications, the CORDIS list also gives visibility to journal articles (e.g., in *Argomenti*, *altlasten spektrum* or the *International Journal of Urban Planning and Smart Cities*), book chapters and conference proceedings not indexed by Scopus (17 out of 60). In addition, extracting publication output from the CORDIS database allows the identification of additional publications that did not show up in my Scopus search: no fewer than 26 publications (in addition to the 17 not indexed by Scopus) that are part of the CORDIS list did not return as search results in Scopus. In other words, there is only limited overlap between the two lists, which seems to be largely a result of my search strategy to identify relevant research projects and the publications linked to these projects. At the same time, many of the authors captured in the CORDIS search also show up in Scopus (but with different or additional publications). Similar thematic foci also return, with publications on brownfield redevelopment, shrinking cities and regions, and the circular economy, but the overall focus seems to be more applied and planning-oriented than various highly cited publications in the Scopus dataset. This is also reflected in the choice of journals, with those such as *Urban Planning* and *European Spatial Research and Policy* gaining more visibility. Lastly, the country affiliations of authors again show a clear centrality for Italy, with

no less than 40 per cent of publications in this list having at least one Italy-based author, followed by Germany (28 per cent) and the Netherlands (20 per cent). Whereas the UK belongs to the trio of most productive countries concerning Scopus-registered output, it is much less visible in this CORDIS dataset (7 per cent), together with virtually all other European countries. Considering that the UK has historically been one of the most successful countries in terms of FP participation, this is somewhat surprising.

A similar exercise is not possible for Interreg projects, as the Keep.eu database does not offer comparable data extraction options that would allow us to generate a list of project output. Nevertheless, even limiting the analysis to project titles, descriptions and partners offers interesting insights. Using the same search string for the Keep.eu database produces a total of 70 projects dealing with urban vacancy, a selection of which is shown in Table 5.

Acronym	Title	Period	Programme
BÉRI	Brownfield's Europe Regeneration Initiative	2000-2006	2000 - 2006 Interreg III C West
CSI	Creating a Setting for Investment	2000-2006	2000 - 2006 North West Europe
Mister	Military and Industrial Sites Reuse	2000-2006	2000 - 2006 Cadres
REVIT	Towards More Effective and Sustainable Brownfield Revitalisation Policies	2000-2006	2000 - 2006 North West Europe
B-TEAM	Brownfield Policy Improvement Task Force	2007-2013	2007 - 2013 Interreg IVC
CIRCUSEF	Circular flow land use management	2007-2013	2007 - 2013 Central Europe
LICI	Lively Cities	2007-2013	2007 - 2013 North West Europe
REPAIR	Realising the Potential of Abandoned Military Sites as an Integral part of Sustainable Urban Community Regeneration	2007-2013	2007 - 2013 URBACT II
SECOND CHANCE	From Industrial Use to Creative Impulse	2007-2013	2007 - 2013 Central Europe
SEEDS	Stimulating Enterprising Environments for Development and Sustainability	2007-2013	2007 - 2013 North Sea Region
TUTUR	Temporary Use as a Tool for Urban Regeneration	2007-2013	2007 - 2013 URBACT II
2nd Chance	Waking up the Sleeping Giants	2014-2020	2014 - 2020 URBACT III
Baltic Urban Lab	Integrated Planning and Partnership Model for Brownfield Regeneration	2014-2020	2014 - 2020 INTERREG V-A Finland - Estonia - Latvia - Sweden (Central Baltic)
DIFFD	From wastelands to gardens. Urban agriculture at the service of disadvantaged populations and cross-border areas	2014-2020	2014 - 2020 INTERREG V-A Belgium - France (France - Wallonie - Vlaanderen)
ENSURE	EuropeAN Sustainable Urbanisation through port city REgeneration	2014-2020	2014 - 2020 ESPON 2020
MAPS	Military Assets as Public Spaces	2014-2020	2014 - 2020 URBACT III
REFILL	REUse of vacant spaces as driving Force for Innovation on Local Level	2014-2020	2014 - 2020 URBACT III
STIMULART	Stimulating CCI in mid-sized urban centres to boost competitiveness	2014-2020	2014 - 2020 INTERREG VB Central Europe
Trans-form	Transformations from Slum to Chic	2014-2020	2014 - 2020 INTERREG V-A Latvia - Lithuania
UL2L	UrbanLinks 2 Landscape	2014-2020	2014 - 2020 Interreg Europe
ARCHETHICS	Dissonant European heritage as labs of democracy	2021-2027	2021 - 2027 Interreg VI-C URBACT IV
IMPETUS	IMproving local Policies on Temporary UseS	2021-2027	2021 - 2027 Interreg VI-C Interreg Europe
Re-Gen	Youth and urban regeneration: let's take back public spaces!	2021-2027	2021 - 2027 Interreg VI-C URBACT IV
ReInd-BBG	Reindustrialisation Following the Brownfield is Better than Greenfield Principle	2021-2027	2021 - 2027 Interreg VI-B Danube

Table 5: Selection of projects dealing with urban vacancy, as registered in Keep.eu

Thematically, there is partial alignment across all the datasets (Scopus, CORDIS and Keep.eu), with the Interreg projects also tackling brownfield regeneration, shrinking cities and regions, land use change and ecological improvement, temporary use and re-activation of vacant spaces. Some more specific topics particular to the Keep.eu database also emerge, with projects around the re-use of military sites, the redevelopment of heritage buildings and the role of youth in appropriating public spaces. By contrast, some of the more critical and perhaps more theoretical work on squatting, the commons or the role of migrants and refugees in relation to vacant spaces seems somewhat lacking in Interreg projects, whereas these issues are quite prominent in the Scopus and CORDIS datasets.

Again, the geography of participation in Interreg programmes and other types of European cross-border, transnational and interregional cooperation is broadly distributed across European space, but strikingly unequal at the same time (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Project partner distribution in Keep.eu registered projects

Entities in Italy and Germany are each involved in no fewer than 40 out of 70 projects, followed by a long and geographically diverse list of other European countries. The dominant presence of Italy and Germany (much less so the UK) throughout the different datasets is confirmed, and we can also observe high participation rates of most countries that likewise perform well regarding Scopus-registered publication output and Framework Programme projects: in particular, Netherlands, Spain, France and Poland. However, it is also apparent that some countries participate actively in European interregional cooperation without this participation translating into more research-intense activities typically associated with Framework Programmes and scientific publications. For example, countries such as Hungary, Croatia, Slovenia, Slovakia and Latvia are regularly involved in interregional cooperation projects, but next to invisible in Scopus and CORDIS. Considering the more applied nature of most Interreg projects, with many of these involving close interaction with and involvement of local administrations, enterprises and civic organisations, it seems likely that many researchers do not have the capacity to ‘convert’ this research into more highly cited publications for international journals (typically captured by Scopus) or to participate in complex consortia for attracting European framework programme funding (as registered in CORDIS).

Thematic review

Following on from this quantitative review of the multi-disciplinary literature on urban vacancy, in the subsequent sections I adopt a more qualitative, interpretive approach and discuss several transversal themes I identified in the above datasets.⁶ In contrast to most of the literature on vacancy that is limited to sub-disciplinary/domain-specific debates (there is a research community focusing on temporary use, another on land use change, etc.), I focus here on three themes that are shared across multiple research fields: i) the politics of terminology, ii) collective agency and the state, and iii) urban vacancy and urbanisation.

The politics of terminology

Vacant land, vacant premises, vacant sites and vacant housing. Brownfields, brown buildings and brownfield development. Greyfield land, underused land, underutilised properties, available land and dormant land. Derelict land, blight and contaminated land. Abandoned landscapes, property abandonment, empty spaces and infill sites. Industrial ruins, new ruins, disurbanisation, shrinking cities and ghost cities. Interstitial spaces, terrain vague, edgelands, interim spaces and wastelands.

What I refer to in this paper by the catch-all phrase of ‘urban vacancy’ has been described and labelled in research, planning debates and activism in many ways, with different terminologies implicitly or explicitly referring to diverging disciplinary engagement with the phenomenon of vacancy, but also to particular politics of vacancy. The literature, in other words, is as much analytical (coining concepts in order to better theorise) as it is normative (mobilising concepts to introduce into civic and political debates new ways of looking at and dealing with vacancy). In this section, I focus on this politics of terminology. Based on the multi-disciplinary dataset, literature on vacancy has approached this issue from at least three different (but overlapping and often complementary) angles: i) creating typology-driven definitions, ii) uncovering and introducing ‘alternative’ vocabularies, and iii) understanding vacancy as a development opportunity.

First, researchers have created typology-driven definitions of vacancy before applying these definitions to often case-specific empirical research. Moroni, De Franco and Bellè

⁶ The quantitative analysis as discussed in the previous sections allowed me to identify patterns in the datasets, specifically concerning topics, journals, country affiliation of authors and changes over time. Starting from already existing domain knowledge, the manual cleaning of the dataset (involving the reading of the titles and abstracts of all documents in the dataset) further familiarised me with the European landscape of research on urban vacancy, adding extra nuance and depth to the analysis. Building on this analysis, and the subsequent reading of more than 200 journal articles, book chapters and project reports, I identified at least three important themes that cut across different research communities. Certainly, a level of subjectivity remains, as the identification of themes is ultimately an interpretive process.

(2020), for example, recognise that there is an existing debate on unused buildings, but deem it too alarmist. To counteract this tendency, they propose paying more critical attention to definitional issues and they highlight the distinction between ‘merely empty’ buildings—‘a building in acceptable maintenance conditions but permanently unused’ (p. 1300)—and ‘truly abandoned’ buildings—‘an unused building which is not fully functional and operational’. Similarly, in their paper on expert perceptions of brownfield redevelopment, Loures and Vaz (2018) consider it ‘necessary to find an agreed and accepted definition not only to avoid misunderstandings, but also to create a common language between each and every single person involved in reclamation processes’ (p. 67). This strand of literature primarily deals with definitional questions as a preliminary methodological step in the overall research process. This is certainly relevant, but also too constraining, as it ignores the extent to which concepts are historical and geographical: they have developed and changed over time and in relation to certain places and objects of research. In other words, concepts cannot be reduced to, but are part and parcel of social networks, struggles and conflicts of interest.

Second, this implies that a substantive *social* scientific investigation of urban vacancy needs to engage with and analyse the social relations underlying the invention, operationalisation and mobilisation of concepts. This task has been pursued by researchers included in my dataset in various ways. An important contribution comes from Jorgensen and Tylecote (2007), who offer a useful historical discussion on the ‘ambivalent feelings’ we experience towards wilderness and wasteland. As these authors argue, ‘a characteristic of wilderness was that its edges very often marked the limit of a human or social territory, either geographically or in terms of the ability to control or police the land’ (p. 447). At the same time, and progressively throughout history, these sites were brought into cultivation, colonised or placed under control. It is this ambivalence that has fascinated people ever since, with wilderness and wasteland also acting as interstitial spaces that ‘exist in the gaps between both power and vernacular landscapes’. Jorgensen and Tylecote (2007) suggest that this particularly applies to ‘areas in which the spontaneous growth of vegetation through natural succession suggests that natural rather than human agencies are in control of shaping the land’ (p. 453). Lastly, these authors also point to the ways in which wasteland was historically often equated with common land, thus linking the discussion on vacant spaces to broader debates on the ownership and use of land. Importantly, this is a non-prescriptive common space and more open to diverse uses than most public spaces, able to ‘fulfil a multiplicity of different roles for different people’ (p. 455).

In the last 10–15 years in particular, much critical research attention has been dedicated to investigating the politics of terminology in more detail, both through substantive empirical research and through the introduction of ‘alternative vocabularies’ (Gandy, 2013) and new

modes of theorising. An important strand of literature has focused specifically on the ecological dimensions of vacant spaces, changing the understandings of urban nature and how we as humans relate to these places. As Gandy argues, we see the emergence of vocabularies—such as ‘interim spaces’ or ‘terrain vague’—that sidestep utilitarian interpretations of wasteland and that instead emphasise the role of vacant spaces in sustaining high levels of biodiversity, as well as alternative social and cultural practices. Foster (2014) offers a concrete example of such an approach in her analysis of the Petite Ceinture abandoned railway ring around Paris, claiming that this infrastructural ‘terrain vague’ allows for experiences that go against the ‘dominant logic of urban development’. The starting point of much of this literature is empirical, in that the coining of new vocabularies is used to direct attention to relevant but under-researched dimensions of vacancy. Nevertheless, the interest in terminology also connects smoothly to theoretical concerns, with researchers showing the potential of using the debate on vacancy as a platform for new modes of theorising and action. For example, O’Callaghan (2018) argues ‘that debates and contestations around “vacancy” and “ruin” do important work in producing post-crisis urban space’ (p. 422), and that we need to understand these debates as ‘inherently tied to particular places’ (p. 422). From a different perspective, in her study on Barcelona’s housing policy, Martínez Alonso (2022) shows how degrowth activists and scholars mobilised around the problem of evictions and vacant housing to push for anti-austerity politics that pay explicit attention to environmental concerns, calling for the re-use of existing buildings instead of new developments, and promoting bottom-up projects such as collective kitchens, urban gardening and networks of care.

The proliferation of ‘alternative’ vocabularies points to the multidimensional ways in which vacancy can be conceptualised and imagined, but in most contexts the narrower and utilitarian understanding of vacancy as a development opportunity remains the dominant ‘mainstream’. Research focusing on this third angle tends to be concerned with the local political economy of development, as well as wider institutional trends that shape the governance of vacancy. Adams, de Sousa and Tiesdell (2010) offer a very useful ‘three-stage policy maturity model’ to analyse the ways in which the policy and political process is structured and gives direction to the development of vacancy. The three stages are as follows: first, understanding the vacancy problem (the paper focuses on brownfield development, but their model is more broadly applicable), second, recognising the potential offered by vacant spaces and gaining political support for development, and third, involving the private sector. As the authors point out, these temporal stages are themselves informed by two sets of influences: the ‘general maelstrom of politics’ (the ebb and flow of political will and commitment, or lack thereof) and ‘the evidence derived from, inter alia, experimentation and testing’ (with new knowledge derived from practice becoming policy learning and extending the range of possible solutions to the ‘problem’ of vacancy) (p. 77). As the authors point out,

in the first stage one can already often observe a narrow understanding of the vacancy problem, with vacancy being interpreted through the lens of a ‘static and growth-led conceptualisation of urban change’ (Freire Trigo, 2020, p. 2) and underpinned by the assumption that vacant spaces are a waste of resources and need to be brought back into productive use.

Experimenting with new approaches can expand the “known” universe of policy solutions’ (Adams et al., 2010), but this is not to be taken for granted, as there are multiple constraints. At the level of market expertise, for example, Adams and Tolson (2019) offer a highly interesting study of the valuation practices of chartered surveyors and the difficulties they encounter in establishing the market value of land within a regeneration context characterised by low demand and a high level of uncertainty. This may delay regeneration activity, as landowners may hold on to unrealistic expectations of land value and/or keep brownfield land off the market based on the belief that its value will increase in the future, thus contributing to long-term vacancy. Related to this, others have argued that the globalisation and financialisation of real estate markets has brought locally available land and property into wider dynamics of speculation, contributing to the development of vacant spaces by ‘abstracting the materiality of property and projecting prospective economic value onto “empty” landscapes, therein vacating present–past space-times in the service of possible capital-rich futures’ (Noterman, 2022, p. 123). However, in periods of crisis and property crashes, we can also observe how these ‘speculative futures’ actively create the very ruins and abandoned sites they claim to want to develop (O’Callaghan et al., 2018). At the level of policy mobility and the local political regime, Honeck (2018) shows the extent to which policy imaginaries are shaped by prevailing narratives that circulate at different administrative scales and between cities. These narratives contribute to collective perceptions among a community of actors and influence actual urban policies. Lastly, a similar situation applies to the level of the broader public debate, with the media shaping dominant perceptions of vacant space and its users (Matoga, 2019; Martínez, 2019; Ivanov, 2021).

Collective agency and the state

Entangled with and building on the research that investigates social relations underlying the invention, operationalisation and mobilisation of concepts (the second research angle discussed in the previous section), much of the academic and civic debate on vacancy is motivated by an interest in vacant spaces as key platforms for building communities and collective modes of agency. In general terms, this implies directing attention to the materiality of vacant spaces, with researchers addressing the role of urban ruins and abandoned landscapes as social (though contested) sites of memory (Edensor, 2005) and as ‘characterized by both the absence of use or function, and by the presence of promise and hope’ (Biddau et

al., 2020, p. 7), a debate also picked up in more applied projects on urban heritage (as discussed in the earlier sections of this paper, e.g., PICTURING and ARCHETHICS). As Biddau, Marotta and Sanna argue, we are accordingly best served by pursuing ‘design methods aimed at creating connections among the different actors affected by a given project’ (2020, p. 8). There are many ways in which connections can be created, but based on my review, at least two reasonably distinct research communities and thematic fields can be identified: i) squatters’ movements and property, and ii) bottom-up urbanism and temporary use.

Research on squatting and its relations to social movements and contestation is well-established within the social sciences—and urban studies specifically—and returns here in this dataset on vacancy. Squatting and social movements research has traditionally paid substantive empirical and theoretical attention to the state as a structuring force. In one of the earliest articles in our dataset, Pruijt (2003) gives centre stage to the problem of the relations between the state and squatting, and argues that the ‘integration’ of the latter into the former can take two different forms: institutionalisation and co-optation. Institutionalisation leads to a change in the action repertoire of movements, with squatters adopting non-confrontational methods instead of or complementing disruptive acts. One outcome can be the legalisation of squats, but state repression is equally possible. Co-optation implies that a state institution ‘embraces certain ideas from the movement, while redefining problems in such a way that solving them does not threaten its own stability’ (Prujt, 2003, p. 136). From the perspective of squatters’ movements, this can be understood either as ‘selling out’ or as an opportunity to change and reform the state institution from within. Pruijt argues that this is theoretically undecidable, needing to be analysed on a case-by-case basis. More recent work has continued researching these state–movements dynamics, for example, Van Schipstal and Nicholls (2014) in their research on how the strategic options available to trailer encampment communities on squatted land in Berlin vary according to the political opportunities at multiple political levels. From a different angle, Ferreri and Vasudevan (2019) show how the rise of property guardianship companies in London as a ‘legal’ way to manage vacant property contributes to, instead of helping to reduce, the further precarisation of housing.

More broadly, much of this debate revolves around the level of autonomy a squatting community can (hope to) achieve. This has been a longstanding concern in social movements literature and is part of the self-identity of most squatting communities. As Martínez López highlights, autonomy implies a separation of activists from institutionalised actors and a strong interest in developing self-managed and decentralised organisations; something also captured by theoretical-political strands such as social anarchism, Italian Operaismo, the Situationist International and autonomist Marxism (Martinez López, 2013). Specific (though not exclusive) to squatting, this concern with autonomy is always rooted in a particular

building and plot of land, and squatters invest substantial energy into making a place inhabitable: Pruijt (2003) already mentions the extent to which the physical condition of buildings shapes squatters' realm of action, Mudu (2004) understands one of the key contributions of squatting to be its role in 'renovating publicly and privately owned vacated properties as an alternative to property speculation' (p. 936), and Abellán, Sequera and Janoschka (2012) argue that occupying buildings can contribute to questioning the hegemonic discourse of individual property rights. In more recent years, this interest in thinking through collective agency, autonomy and property has been picked up by literature on urban commoning, including research on more institutionalised forms, such as community land trusts (Thompson, 2015; Arvanitidis and Papagiannitsis, 2020), as well as research and activism around housing evictions and the occupation of bank-owned empty housing by movements such as the Plataforma de Afectados por la Hipoteca (PAH) in Spain (García-Lamarca, 2017).

From social movements to alter-globalisation and to the mobility of migrants, research on squatting and vacancy has always been aware of how squatted sites are both 'local' and 'global' at the same time. Analyses of squatted properties functioning as social centres—which can include housing and are often mixed-use, but with a strong focus on social, political and cultural events—emphasise the role of specific buildings and directly-involved actors within the wider urban to even global ecosystem of organising, activism and squatting. As again Martínez López (2013) argues, squatted social centres in particular serve as an 'essential socio-spatial infrastructure for the coordination and public expression of the squatting movement as a political urban agent' (p. 867). This infrastructure provides opportunities to meet activists from different social movements, inside and outside of the squatting networks, and offers opportunities for people to 'experiment with alternative and communal modes of living' (p. 879). Beyond the concern with the position of squatting within the urban context, much of the literature in the 1990s and 2000s investigates the linkages between local squatting activity and wider alter-globalisation networks and politics, emphasising the role of alter-global discourses as well as the rise of digital communication modes and increased mobility due to the greater availability of cheap flights. From the second half of the 2010s onwards, this has moved towards an interest in the position of migrants within and in relation to squatters' movements. As part of this shift in empirical focus, the theoretical vocabulary used has also changed. Squatting is still an empirical focus, but is increasingly understood through the lens of citizenship, commons or informality (Martínez López, 2017; Pradel-Miquel, 2017; Montagna and Grazioli, 2019; Raimondi, 2019; Tsavdaroglou et al., 2019; Tsavdaroglou and Kaika, 2022). Squatted properties remain privileged places for interaction and meeting people from different communities and movements, but also sites where dominant squatting identities are challenged while seeing the introduction of new solidarities, as well as

inequalities between different groups. For example, as Pradel-Miquel (2017) argues in his paper on sub-Saharan migrants occupying abandoned factories in Barcelona, we can observe an “uneven politicization” of informal practices’, with more recent arrivals, such as sub-Saharan migrants, having ‘more difficulties linking their demands to larger political struggles’ and with their informal activities ‘more easily repressed by the city council’ (pp. 215–216).

A second body of research within this larger theme of collective agency and the state also approaches the built environment from a logic of appropriation, but in contrast to squatting, tends to be more interested in temporary interventions and (not always, but often) more pragmatic ways of theorising informing urban practice. Tonkiss’ (2013) paper on ‘the makeshift city’ captures this spirit well. Acknowledging the impact of austerity urbanism on urban space and the extent to which the retrenchment of the local state necessitates community-led and voluntary initiatives taking on responsibility for basic public services, Tonkiss nevertheless highlights the importance of interstitial urban practices to the design of what Lynch terms the ‘possible city’; practices that go against the grain of urban development as usual through the ‘re-making of space *in time* – such that different sites can decelerate the rhythms of the city’ and with the capacity to ‘refigure the city around spaces that were dormant, disregarded or dead’ (p. 322). This type of situated interest in the political and utopian potential of specific and often vacant sites in our cities is shared by various authors (e.g., Till and McArdle, 2015; Jiménez, 2017; Müller and Trubina, 2020; Milan and Milan, 2021; Besana, 2021) and is central to multiple projects funded through Interreg or European framework programmes (e.g., IMPETUS, TUTUR, URBAN CATALYSTS, gE.CO Living Lab and NOMAD), but should not obscure the extent to which these initiatives are regularly incorporated in longer-term planning and urban development schemes. Madanipour (2018) highlights this dimension, arguing that ‘empty urban spaces are an integral part of the urban development processes and the products of the temporal and spatial fluctuations that are inherent in capitalism’ (p. 1095). According to him, the temporary use of space is just one of four techniques to induce flexibility in spatial production, next to price adjustment, supply reduction and functional conversion, and has become a key instrument in ‘filling the gap’ until growth-oriented development strategies again attract enough capacity for investment. This turns temporary urbanism into a profoundly contradictory and ‘Janus-faced’ process (Bragaglia and Rossignolo, 2021).

More broadly, this relates temporary urbanism to wider planning institutions and practices, and connects the debate on vacancy to planning literature on legal frameworks as well as citizen participation (e.g., Amenta et al., 2015). Patti and Polyak (2015) offer the most hands-on overview, emphasising that government administrations and related actors (architectural offices, development agencies, commercial enterprises, etc.) have become

increasingly involved in the governance of vacancy over recent decades, in turn contributing to the transformation of planning itself. These authors highlight various ways in which administrations aim to support temporary use: by developing an overview of vacant properties, by mediating between owners and (potential) users, by introducing vacant property taxes or, conversely, financial incentives to encourage the reuse of vacant spaces, and by developing more flexible planning regulations and permission procedures for temporary use. This latter point in particular has been highlighted throughout the temporary use literature in recent decades, but can easily fall into the trap of entrepreneurial urbanism identified by Ferreri (2020) and others. Avoiding this necessitates the development of 'careful rental agreements and value capture frameworks, taking into account users' investments in the properties both in terms of financial and energy resources' (Patti and Polyak, 2015, p. 129). Patti and Polyak identify new, community-based property development models that allow citizens to gain collective ownership of the building they operate in, as one important example of such an agreement and a value capture framework (see also the reference above to commoning and community land trusts). This community-based approach can diversify urban land use and contribute to a broader vision of urban sustainability, which requires participatory platforms to bring together diverse stakeholders to collectively define the use of vacancy (Moore-Cherry and McCarthy, 2016). It also has the potential to re-politicise current planning cultures that are often interpreted as depoliticised or overly technical (Rossini and Bianchi, 2020).

Vacancy and urbanisation

Most literature on urban vacancy is concerned with specific sites or even buildings within particular urban neighbourhoods, reflecting a situated theoretical and qualitative research approach, as well as a hands-on interest in safeguarding specific places from speculative urban development: be it in the form of community gardens, squatted housing or socio-cultural spaces. In this last section, I want to discuss strands in the literature that move beyond these more 'local' concerns, and that analyse the relationship of urban vacancy to broader urbanisation dynamics. Approaching this regional question from the perspective of shrinking cities, Martinez-Fernandez et al. (2012) and Haase et al. (2014) emphasise that studying urban shrinkage, population losses and resultant urban vacancy is nothing new, and they start their articles with summary reviews of the wider body of urban and regional studies literature addressing these issues. For instance, Martinez-Fernandez et al. (2012) refer to Hoyt's cyclic approach to urban change, Kondratieff's cycle theory and Schumpeter's 'creative destruction', as well as 1980s–90s literature on evolutionary theories of urban development and critical political economy research on economic disinvestment as an explanation for neighbourhood decline. Similarly, Haase et al. (2014) contextualise urban shrinkage, referring to earlier debates on life-cycle theories of urban development, suburbanisation, accumulation of capital

and its uneven spatial-temporal circulation, territorial divisions of labour and demographic change. From the perspective of land use change and landscape ecology, Serra et al. (2014) argue that to analyse spatial changes in the urban–rural relationship, we need to investigate both land intensification and land extensification, with the former referring to ‘increased population density along the urban gradient due to settlement density and a higher vertical profile in urban areas’ (p. 71) and the latter mainly linked to ‘(partial or complete) land abandonment and depopulation’ (p. 72). Somewhat surprisingly, considering the amount of research on land abandonment and vacant spaces conducted by environmental scholars, land economists and landscape researchers (also very much apparent in the lists of funded Framework Programme and Interreg projects, such as GREENSCOM, REPAiR, CIRCUSE and UL2L), this body of literature remains somewhat distanced from the core urban studies and planning literature on vacancy, both theoretically and empirically.

One can identify at least two thematic strands that engage with vacancy from a more meso-level perspective and that in doing so aim to tackle the question of vacancy in relation to urbanisation. First, the sprawling and interdisciplinary body of literature on infrastructure is also picked up in the research on shrinking cities, arguing that rapid population decline causes an urban infrastructure that is ‘too large’ for its population, leading in turn to policy proposals and practices of demolition as urban development strategies (Bontje, 2004; Haase et al., 2014). Both actual population decline and infrastructure demolition contribute to ‘perforated land use patterns, i.e. decreasing housing densities, abandoned sites and urban brownfields’ (Schetke and Haase, 2008, p. 484), a topic also picked up by many European-funded projects (e.g., SHRINK SMART, RE-CITY, B-TEAM and Baltic Urban Lab). This debate connects to the literature on peripheralisation, as one needs to understand the development opportunities for these ‘losing’ peripheral regions in relation to the broader dynamics of uneven spatial development and the powerful economic and demographic pull of ‘winning’ metropolitan regions (Lang, 2012). The discursive dimension of this cannot be underestimated: the centre-periphery distinction regularly leads to collective self-images of failure and being on the margins of society. As Bennett (2021) highlights in her paper on ‘post-post-Soviet-ruins’ in Russia, ideological promises are tightly linked to infrastructure, and infrastructural decline contributes to a sense of peripheralisation. This ruination of infrastructure has been extensively studied by various authors (Edensor, 2005; Mah, 2012; O’Callaghan, 2018; Brito-Henriques and Cruz, 2019). Bennett (2021) urges us not just to consider urban ruination in relation to its economic drivers (creative destruction and neighbourhood disinvestment), but also to pay attention to how the geopolitical push to realise megaprojects and large-scale building developments actively contributes to peripheralisation, infrastructure decline and vacancy in other areas of a city. The intricate link between speculative development and urban vacancy has also been apparent in other parts of the world, particularly in periods of crisis, as

has been shown extensively in literature on Ireland (Moore-Cherry, 2015; Corcoran et al., 2017; O'Callaghan, 2018) and Spain (Díaz-Parra and Mena, 2015; Burriel, 2016; García-Lamarca, 2017). For example, Burriel (2016) provides very convincing evidence of how the bursting of the Spanish housing bubble has created a huge stock of vacant land in different phases of development, creating three types of 'empty' urban spaces: ghost towns (developed areas, but without inhabitants), urbanised deserts (areas provided with the necessary infrastructure, such as streets and electricity, but without houses) and captive land (agricultural land legally reclassified as urban land ripe for development, but without any development as yet).

A second transversal theme concerns urban expansion. Symptomatic of the divide between the social scientific and the environmental research communities, this theme is largely approached from two distinct angles. Inner-city population decline has already been identified in the discussed literature on shrinking cities, but more broadly there is a long-standing tradition of research on urban sprawl and suburbanisation, with specific consequences for inner-city urban vacancy (Power, 2001; Townshend, 2006; de Decker, 2011). In an important paper on housing sprawl in Flanders, Belgium, De Decker (2011) argues that housing policies are path dependent, with previous political choices, cultural-social preferences for nonurban single-family houses and fiscal incentives still shaping the present and leading to a relative out-migration of people from inner cities (only partially compensated for by international migration). The development of second homes has also been linked to urban expansion and suburbanisation, or even the 'urbanisation' of the more-distant countryside through the influx of populations from urban areas. For example, in their paper on post-socialist *dachas* in the Tallinn metropolitan area, Leetmaa et al. (2012) point to how the stock of vacant summer-home settlements supported the suburbanisation of the housing market after construction restrictions were lifted. This connects to a related debate on second homes and the gentrification or 'urbanisation' of the countryside, which also shows up in the dataset. Solana-Solana (2010) presents a case study of a rural area in Catalonia, Spain, to show how 'residential tourism' leads to a more important role for the countryside as leisure and residential space. As he argues, this leads to conflicts between lifestyles, with local inhabitants struggling to still find affordable housing, with services and facilities catering more to the (wealthier) newcomers from the cities than to the local population and with the agricultural landscape increasingly threatened by residential growth. In this example, the urbanisation of the countryside leads to a partial (if contested) revitalisation of an area, but in turn also produces vacancy, with many of these second homes remaining empty for most of the year and with some villages becoming ghost communities (Vaccaro and Beltran, 2007).

This leads me to the second angle on urban expansion, namely the land use and environmental studies literature, and its interest in how urban expansion relates to environmental quality. La Rosa et al. (2014) offer a succinct summary of the key dimensions of this debate. Urban expansion, as they rightly argue, is not simply an effect of demographic development, and one can observe partial decoupling throughout Europe: despite decreasing populations in many regions, urban expansion has continued apace. This is particularly visible at the fringes of cities ‘where uncontrolled urban development is often characterized by discontinuous patterns and consequent fragmentation of farmlands’ (p. 290), in turn resulting in a dramatic decrease of non-urbanised areas within these city regions. To counter this trend, the authors point to research on new types of multifunctional urban agriculture, such as urban farms, allotment gardens and agricultural parks. Even though this type of use is hardly new, continuing the longstanding tradition of allotment gardens for individual/household use, in recent decades we have seen substantial mobilisation around the collective governance of urban food production, distribution and consumption. Connecting with the literature on infrastructure, La Rosa et al. (2014) propose that at the city-regional scale, the focus should be on creating an ‘agricultural greenway network’ that connects different plots of urban agriculture and that can provide different types of ecosystem services. Case study research from across Europe exists, but in particular there is a great deal of work dealing with southern European cities (e.g., Calvet-Mir and March, 2019; Mudu and Marini, 2018; Simon-Rojo, 2019; Gasperi et al., 2016; Cattivelli, 2020). However, the continuing pressure of real estate driven urban development on this ‘non-urban’ land is somewhat underdeveloped in the literature. Without robust planning regulations and protection measures, the land will remain subject to a variety of conflicting interests. Land price rises and increased competition over land use are the results, tending to favour urban residential use at the expense of other functions (Casanova Enault et al., 2021). Countering urban sprawl by mapping ‘empty’ urban areas such as brownfield sites, vacant plots and underused plots in order to identify ‘urban infill development potential’ (Schiller et al., 2021) is a valuable undertaking and could potentially contribute to limiting urban expansion at city fringes. Nevertheless, this approach in turn runs the risk of further densifying city cores, with limited attention paid to the ecological value of non-built urban sites. Lastly, as part of this debate there is a growing strand of literature that tackles the urban question from a rural perspective by investigating the impact of land abandonment on rural regions. Much research on this topic has studied the European Mediterranean, a region that has high levels of biodiversity, yet that is also heavily subject to the ‘abandonment of rural, mountainous and less economically developed areas on one side, and agricultural intensification, urbanization and increasing human pressures on the other’ (Quintas-Soriano et al., 2022, p. 2). Urbanisation and industrialisation, in other words, play a driving role in farmland abandonment.

Notes towards a research agenda

This paper offers a synthetic review of research on urban vacancy across the social sciences, ranging from studies on temporary use, squatting and urban ruins, to land use change, brownfield redevelopment and ecosystem services. To the best of my knowledge, this is the first review on urban vacancy to cover so many research domains. In this last part, I focus on a number of observations that cut transversally across the different domains. These can hopefully function as notes towards an interdisciplinary research agenda on urban vacancy—specifically, a research agenda that is sensitive to the embeddedness and context of urban vacancy research, and that understands urban vacancy as exhibiting and harbouring practices of experimentation that prefigure new and more sustainable ways of urban living. The focus of my paper is on urban vacancy in Europe, and the proposed research agenda accordingly relates primarily to the European context. I would nevertheless like to think that my observations are also relevant to urban vacancy research in other regions of the world.

First, and even though the North-South and West-East divides often observed in the European publication landscape (van Heur, 2024) do not really hold in the case of urban vacancy research, we can still observe an uneven landscape of publication output and projects, but one with different patterns depending on the dataset discussed. In the case of Scopus-registered publications, the United Kingdom, Italy and Germany together produce almost half of all publications, although we can also identify a long list of countries with a still substantial number of publications on urban vacancy: from Switzerland to Finland and from Romania to Ireland. However, zooming in on the most-cited publications already shows a much more skewed geography: whereas publications of authors based in the UK, Italy or Germany also belong among the most-cited, there are very few authors affiliated with Central or South-eastern European institutions that make it to this list. At the same time, we can also observe geographic shifts over time, as we can see a relative decline of the UK and Germany in recent years and a strong increase in particular of publication output linked to Italy-based authors. A mix of shifting thematic interests (e.g., a decline of research on shrinking cities in Germany), journal choice (e.g., the increase in cited publication output for Italy co-developing with the substantial increase of papers published in the MDPI-journal *Sustainability*) and citation bias (e.g., with authors based in Western or Southern European countries and publishing in journals with a strong international profile receiving the most citations) seem to offer at least partial explanations.

The mapping of publications and projects as registered in CORDIS and Keep.eu provides us with an overlapping but also diverging structure. Similar thematic foci return, but the overall concerns are more applied and planning-oriented than several highly cited publications in the Scopus dataset. Journals such as *Urban Planning* and *European Spatial*

Research and Policy gain more visibility in this dataset and, more broadly, we can observe a stronger diversity of publication outlets, with journal articles, book chapters or conference proceedings that are not indexed by Scopus. Italy and Germany (not the UK) dominate both the CORDIS and Keep.eu lists, even though especially for the Interreg projects (unsurprisingly, considering the regional cross-border setup of this funding scheme), almost all European countries participate actively in interregional cooperation. That said, when comparing the datasets, it becomes clear that several Eastern European countries participate in Interreg projects but do not translate this work into more research-intense activities typically associated with Framework Programmes and Scopus-registered scientific publications. As I have highlighted, it seems likely that this reflects limited institutional research capacity that would allow researchers to ‘convert’ their applied work with local administrations, enterprises and organisations into more highly cited publications for international journals or to participate in complex consortia for attracting European framework programme funding. It would be interesting to see future research addressing in greater depth the underlying political economy shaping this uneven landscape of research. Recent work has started to offer this form of cross-case and cross-disciplinary theorisation (e.g., O’Callaghan, 2023), and the current synthetic review paper aims to offer a first contribution to this debate.

Second, the importance of vacant spaces as multifunctional, mixed-use spaces is highlighted across the different bodies of literature discussed. Design and scenario-oriented scholars point to the role of experimentation with vacancy in enabling connections between different types of actors. Research on squatting shows how squats are often important gathering places for distinct urban associations, and combine housing with social, political and cultural functions. Research on rural gentrification also points to how the redevelopment of vacant housing into second homes can create lifestyle conflicts between the urban newcomers mostly buying and renovating these homes and the local population, with services and facilities changing as a result of the demographic shift. However, these observations tend to remain somewhat at the margins of the core focus of each research domain, and a more substantive analysis of the multi-functional and multi-user dimensions of vacancy would benefit from an explicit mobilisation of multiple disciplines in concrete research projects.

Third, much research on urban vacancy is not only case specific, but also often site-specific or even ‘localist’ in its concerns. Admittedly, theoretical contextualisation is well developed across the research domains studied in this paper (ranging from theories on commons to social movements to uneven development, etc.), but much less empirical attention is paid to the networked and multi-scalar dimensions of urban vacancy. That said, we can observe various elements that can help us to develop this research focus more

substantively. Most obviously, existing work on urban infrastructures, suburbanisation and sprawl, and peripheralisation, as well as the more environmental literature on urban expansion and land use change, has always been attuned to the wider regional dimensions of urban vacancy. Research on squatting, particularly in the 1990s and 2000s, heavily invested in studying the connections between squatting and ‘alter-globalisation’ as an emergent form of collective agency. However, this global focus sometimes obscured the importance of the urban hinterland and the immediate region. Research on temporary use also predominantly remains very site-specific in the literature, although here we can also observe how the increasing interest in long-term funding and legal schemes (commons, cooperative or otherwise) pushes the debate towards broader scales of governance. Future research in this area could thus build on already-existing insights into urban vacancy, but would also benefit from engaging more explicitly with related debates on urban peripheries (Phelps et al., 2023) and regional autonomy and spatial justice (Blondel and Evrard, 2019).

Fourth and last, environmental concerns remain somewhat underdeveloped in most of the literature on urban vacancy, with the exception of research on urban agriculture, urban wasteland ecologies and regional land use change. Yet very little attention has been paid to this aspect in the research domains where most of the theoretical development on urban vacancy has taken place over recent decades. It is virtually absent in research on squatting, with the exception of occasional engagements with degrowth, environmental economics and political ecology. Due to its conceptual proximity to urban transitions literature, research on temporary use and urban experimentation pays attention to environmental questions, but is mostly limited to site-specific concerns. In addition, from an urban development and policy point of view, many of these local experiments ultimately contribute to a further densification of the city core, with limited attention given to the ecological value of non-built urban areas. If anything, as discussed in the section on the politics of terminology, we need to expand the ‘known’ universe of solutions by acknowledging the intertwinement of environmental and social dynamics, by pushing for development that understands vacant sites as part of wider socio-ecological urban infrastructures and by recognising the intricate interdependence between the urban and its regional hinterland.

Acknowledgements

This research was developed in the context of the Innoviris-funded project (2022-PRB-4) ‘WELCOMIN: Welfare community mixed infrastructures: Reclaiming vacancy, federating capacities and empowering communities towards an ecological welfare’. I would like to thank several of my colleagues at the Cosmopolis Centre for Urban Research, Vrije Universiteit Brussel, and the anonymous reviewers for their comments on earlier versions of this article.

Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest has been identified.

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